

Complexation equilibria of cephalixin with Hg^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}

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The proton ligand stability constants ($\log K_1^{\text{H}}$, $\log K_2^{\text{H}}$) of antibiotic drug cephalixin and stepwise stability constants ($\log K_1$, $\log K_2$) of its complexes with Hg^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} have been determined potentiometrically in ethanol-water systems [20 : 80, 40 : 60 and 60 : 40 (%v/v)] at 25, 35 and 45°C and 0.05, 0.10 and 0.20 M (KNO_3) ionic strength. The values of $\log K_1^{\text{H}}$ and $\log K_2^{\text{H}}$ as well as $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ decrease with the increasing ionic strengths while increase with increasing ethanol concentrations. The values of thermodynamic stability constants ($\log \beta_2$, $\mu = 0$) have been found to be 11.02, 9.56 and 12.98 in case of Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} respectively at 25°C in 20 : 80 (%v/v) ethanol-water mixtures. Based on this data, the stability order for various metal ions was found to be $\text{Hg}^{\text{II}} > \text{Zn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Cd}^{\text{II}}$. The values of ΔH and ΔS are both negative, thereby, indicating that the complexation is favored by enthalpy changes.

Cephalixin falls under the category of β -lactam antibiotic drugs and is used particularly in the treatment of skin infections. The metal complexation behaviour of several cephalosporins based on potentiometric titrations has been reported some time ago¹. In the present investigations, the protonation constants of cephalixin and metal-ligand formation constants of its complexes with Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} in ethanol-water systems (20 : 80, 40 : 60 and 60 : 40 %v/v) at 25, 35 and 45°C and 0.05, 0.10 and 0.20 M ionic strength have been determined by pH titration technique. The thermodynamic stability constants, free energy changes (ΔG), enthalpy changes (ΔH) and entropy changes (ΔS) involved in the formation of complexes are also reported.

Results and discussion

Proton-ligand stability constants :

The protonated cephalixin molecule (Scheme 1) loses two protons in the pH range 3–7 corresponding to the ionization of carboxylic group ($\text{I} \rightleftharpoons \text{II}$) and protonated N atom of NH_3^+ group ($\text{II} \rightleftharpoons \text{III}$). The values of proton ligand stability constants ($\log K_1^{\text{H}}$ and $\log K_2^{\text{H}}$) with error limits ± 0.02 log units are given in Table 1.

It is evident from the data that $\log K_1^{\text{H}}$ and $\log K_2^{\text{H}}$ values decrease with the increasing ionic strength and temperature, while increases with increasing ethanol concentration in ethanol-water mixtures. Here it should be noted that, as predicted by born equation, the creation of charge in media of low dielectric constant is an unfavor-

Scheme 1

able process and hence resulting in greater $\log K_1^{\text{H}}$ and $\log K_2^{\text{H}}$ values which follows the order 60 : 40 > 40 : 60 > 20 : 80 ethanol-water (%v/v) mixtures.

Metal-cephalexin stability constants :

The titration curves reveal that complexation occurred below pH 6.5 in various ethanol-water mixtures for different metal ions. The \bar{n} values lies between 0–2 indicating the formation of ML and ML_2 complexes for each metal ion. The values of the metal-ligand stability constants ($\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ and $\log \beta_2$) for various metal-ligand systems are given in Table 1. The error limits are ± 0.02 log units for $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values. Similar to $\log K_1^{\text{H}}$ and $\log K_2^{\text{H}}$, these values decrease with an increase of ionic strength and temperature. The lesser stability at higher ionic strengths may be due to the decreased activity of the metal ion for its interaction with

Table 1. Proton-ligand stability constants of cephalixin and its metal-ligand stability constants at various ionic strengths (0.05, 0.10 and 0.20), temperatures (25, 35 and 45°C) and ethanol-water mixtures (20 : 80, 40 : 60 and 60 : 40 %v/v)

Cation	Temp. (°C)	Ionic strength (M)	Ethanol : Water (% v/v)	Constant			
				log K_1^H	log K_2^H	log β_2^H	
H ⁺	25	0.05		6.58	3.60	10.18	
		0.10	20 : 80	6.42	3.43	9.95	
		0.20			3.35	9.77	
	25	0.05	40 : 60	6.60	3.70	10.3	
			60 : 40	6.65	3.80	9.91	
	35	0.05	20 : 80	6.50	3.50	10.00	
	45			6.36	3.26	9.62	
	Zn ^{II}	25	0.05	20 : 80	5.10	4.68	9.78 (11.02)
			0.10		3.91	3.78	7.69
			0.20		3.74	3.43	7.17
25		0.05	40 : 60	5.20	4.94	10.14	
			60 : 40	5.39	5.00	10.39	
35		0.05	20 : 80	4.60	4.01	8.61	
45				4.38	3.89	8.27	
Cd ^{II}		25	0.05	20 : 80	4.65	3.92	8.57 (9.56)
			0.10		3.76	3.08	6.84
			0.20		3.61	2.39	6.00
	25	0.05	40 : 60	4.90	4.10	9.00	
			60 : 40	5.17	4.29	9.45	
	35	0.05	20 : 80	4.30	3.78	8.08	
	45			3.74	3.02	6.76	
	Hg ^{II}	25	0.05	20 : 80	6.38	6.10	12.48 (12.98)
			0.10		4.80	4.10	8.81
			0.20		4.60	4.38	8.98
25		0.05	40 : 60	6.84	5.85	12.69	
			60 : 40	7.30	6.24	13.64	
35		0.05	20 : 80	5.20	5.08	10.28	
45				5.06	4.56	9.26	

The values in parenthesis are thermodynamic stability constants (log β_2 , $\mu = 0$).

other species present in the solution. The stability constants of the complexes increase as the ethanol content of the medium increases from 20% to 40% and further from 40% to 60% in ethanol-water mixtures at 25°C. This is because the dielectric constant of the medium decreases with the increasing percentage of ethanol and association of species varies inversely with the dielectric constant of the medium. The observed stability order for the metal ions towards cephalixin was found to be : Hg^{II} > Zn^{II} > Cd^{II}. A correlation between the log β_2 of the complexes and the ionization potential has been reported in literature² and similar correlation has been observed in

the present studies.

Thermodynamic functions :

The thermodynamic stability constants of the complexes (Table 1) were obtained at 25°C by plotting log β_2 versus $\mu^{1/2}$ and extrapolating to zero ionic strength. The free energy changes (ΔG) and entropy changes (ΔS) involved in the formation of complexes were calculated by the following relationships :

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K \text{ and } \Delta G = \Delta H - T \Delta S$$

The enthalpy changes (ΔH) were obtained from the relation :

$$\Delta H = -2.303 RS_1,$$

where, S_1 is the slope from the linear plot of $\log \beta_2$ versus $1/T$ (T = temperature in Kelvin). The negative value of ΔG in the case of all the complexes suggests the spontaneous formation of complexes. The enthalpy changes (ΔH) and the entropy changes (ΔS) also have negative values for all the complexes. The enthalpy term is favorable while the entropy term is unfavorable as is evident from the negative values (Table 2).

Table 2. Free energy, enthalpy and entropy change data of metal(II) cephalixin complexes in 20 : 80 (%v/v) ethanol-water concentration and at 0.05 M ionic strength

Metal ion	Temp. (°C)	$-\Delta H$ (kcal mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta G$ (kcal mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S$ (cal deg ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
Zn ^{II}	25		13.33	62.75
	35	32.03	12.13	64.60
	45		12.03	62.87
Cd ^{II}	25		11.68	63.08
	35	31.11	11.38	64.05
	45		9.83	69.09
Hg ^{II}	25		17.01	61.60
	35	36.60	14.48	69.55
	45		13.47	72.73

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. Cephalixin was procured from Glaxo India Ltd. A digital pH-meter Model PH 5652A (Electric Corporation of India Ltd.) with a glass and calomel electrode assembly, reading up to 0.01 units, was used to follow the change in pH during the titrations. The Bjerrum-Calvin pH titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti was used for the titrations. For pH titrations, the following thermostated solu-

tions were titrated against carbonate free 0.1 M KOH solution. (a) 4 ml 0.05 M HNO₃, (b) a + 5 ml 0.004 M cephalixin and (c) b + 2.50 ml 0.004 M metal ion solution. The ionic strength (0.05, 0.10 and 0.20 M) was adjusted by adding calculated amount of 1 M KNO₃ and the total initial volume of the solution were kept 50 ml by adding appropriate quantity of double distilled water and ethanol. The plots of pH values against volume of KOH added were drawn. The values of \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and pL were calculated using the Irving-Rossotti method³ and proton-ligand stability constants ($\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$) and metal-ligand stability constants ($\log K_1$, $\log K_2$) were obtained by using half integral and other computational methods³.

References

1. P. C. Van Krimpen, W. P. Bennekorn and A. Bult Neth, *Pharm. Weekbl., Sci. Ed.*, 1988, **10**, 259; J. R. Anaconda, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2001, **54**, 355; P. B. Chakrawarti, M. Chakrawarti and P. Maini, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **77**, 85, 217; M. J. Lozano and S. J. Borrás, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 1987, **31**, 187; M. G. Ahmed, F. Akhtar and M. G. Moula, *J. Bangladesh Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **10**, 17; M. S. Iqbal, A. R. Ahmad, M. Sabir and S. M. Asad, *Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 1999, **51**, 371; A. A. Abdel-Gaber, O. A. Farghaly, M. A. Ghandour and H. S. El-Said, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 2000, **131**, 1031; S. I. Al-Resayes, *J. Saudi Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **5**, 205; G. N. Mukherjee and T. K. Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1994, **71**, 49; M. I. H. Helaleh and E. S. M. Nameh, *Ann. Quim. Int. Ed.*, 1998, **94**, 160; F. M. Abdel-Gawad, N. M. El-Guindi and M. N. Ibrahim, *J. Drug Res.*, 1987, **17**, 197; J. M. Moratal, J. Borrás, A. Donaire and M. J. Martínez, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1989, **162**, 113; V. Kapetanovic, D. Vasinovic and D. Suznjevic, *Anal. Letts.*, 1990, **23**, 857; *Electroanal.*, 1990, **2**, 48; R. Vitturi, M. Colomba, L. Ronconi, I. D. Sciacca and L. Pellerito, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2004, **98**, 534.
2. P. B. Chakrawarti and B. Shrivastva, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **70**, 158.
3. H. M. Irving and H. S. Rossotti, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397; 1954, 2904.